

TALENT MANAGEMENT OF MISSIONARY SALES FORCE FOR LOW ATTRITION RATE: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF SELECTED PHARMACEUTICAL COMPANIES

Mr. Anjan Kumar Mohanty

*Lecturer, Department of BBA,
Ravenshaw University, Cuttack

Dr. Tushar Kanta Pany

**Associate Professor,
School of Commerce and Management Studies,
Ravenshaw University, Cuttack

Abstract

Missionary Selling is a form of indirect selling in which a salesperson tries to provide information about the given product to an individual who has an influence on the buying decision rather than directly selling the product. This is used to convince a person who has never used a product to buy it. Missionary sales are common in technical, pharmaceuticals and text books. The pharmaceutical industry is growing exponentially; there is a constant thirst for the best and the brightest of employees. After IT sector, the pharmaceuticals industry is grappling with the highest level of attrition rate of 30 to 35 per cent, according to a recent survey of Indian pharmaceutical companies by Interlink Marketing Consultancy. Job satisfaction had a positive influence on organization commitment and a negative influence on turnover intentions. The differences in job satisfaction across age and experience categories were not significant but salespersons with higher educational qualifications reported lower levels of job satisfaction. The talent management has arisen as a big task for pharmaceutical industry to consolidate their growth; thus in this paper talent management strategy of missionary sales people in pharmaceutical industry for reducing their attrition rate are discussed. The causes of attrition like money factor, working conditions, organization's culture, opportunities for growth, organization behavior, low self-esteem, plateaued sales person etc are discussed. Roles of human resource management in meeting organizational needs and tasks have also been discussed. Strategies to attract best talents, retain and motivate talented people, psychological environment, and career track management are also discussed in this study. Organizational environment like work culture, engaged leaders, effective communication practices, challenging assignments, differentiate rewards for superior performers like financial and non financial benefits, growth opportunities, training programmes, flexible work-time, quality of life, work-life-balance, MBO practices, posting in the local areas, assignment of higher responsibility and accountability to plateaued sales people who are above the age group of 45 can help them to retain in the organization for longer period of time and reduce attrition rate in the organization resulting improvement in productivity.

Keywords: *Missionary Selling, Attrition Rate, Talent Management, Job satisfaction, plateaued sales people, MBO practices, flexible work-time, quality of life, work-life-balance*

Introduction:

Sales Department plays a very important role in organization. It is the only department which generates revenue for the organization. Sales forces are the brand ambassadors of the organization and the success of the organization depends upon the successful sales force management. Retention of quality sales force particularly in pharmaceutical sectors has become very challenging. Organizations spend lots of money and put valuable time for searching talented people, select them, but fail in retaining them for long period.

Mohanty& Pany/ Talent Management Of Missionary Sales Force For Low Attrition Rate

Missionary Selling is a form of indirect selling in which a salesperson tries to provide information about the given product to an individual who has an influence on the buying decision rather than directly selling the product. This is used to convince a person who has never used a product to buy it.

Missionary sales are common in technical, pharmaceuticals, text books, life insurance and other financial products. Technical organizations depend on system specialists to be their mystery sellers. These specialists generally work with customers to identify and solve their technical and operational issues while providing them information about the products which might solve these problems. Similarly salespersons of textbooks target professors by giving them free samples of books who in turn might recommend their students to purchase the same.

Likewise, pharmaceutical detailers, instead of selling their products directly to doctors or medical practitioners, provide them with brochures and pamphlets containing information about the product who then determine whether the medicines can be prescribed to their patients. A pharmaceutical detailer must have thorough knowledge about his product and must be able to answer the doctor's queries to utmost satisfaction in order to convince him to prescribe the medicine to his patients.

The pharmaceutical industry is growing tremendously; companies are focusing from survival strategy to competitive strategy. There is a constant search for the best and the brightest of employees. The ever growing industry is facing the problem of heavy attrition. After information technology, the pharmaceuticals industry is grappling with the highest level of attrition. The fast growing knowledge-based sector suffers an annual attrition rate of 30 to 35 per cent, according to a recent survey by Interlink Marketing Consultancy. Interlink surveyed a sample of 15 companies in the small, medium and large segments in the Indian pharmaceutical sector. The survey points out that the sector's high churn other than the natural rate of attrition is mainly due to **poaching, burnout, high stress at work and inadequate payment**. Globally, the rate of attrition in pharmaceutical is only 10 to 12 per cent, says the IBS report. The research reveals that the pharmaceutical industry annually experiences an employee turnover of 30 to 40 per cent at the field level and 8 to 10 per cent at the managerial level.

Supply vs. demand

Attrition is the function of demand and supply. The industry has continuous demand of experienced employees and globalization has created the need of fresh talent for incorporating new ideas. "The demand comes from the growth of the industry and the policy of the company. These two things decide whether there is a demand of fresher or experienced employees. On the other hand, the supply comes from the educational institutions and the market. The supply from the educational institutions is enough to meet the demands of the pharmaceutical industry but, there is a lack of experienced people in the industry, which in turn has created an imbalance. Organizations fail to nurture the talent of young people because of faulty recruitment policies and lack of proper strategies to groom, motivate and retain young talents.

OBJECTIVES

- To find out the reasons for employee attrition in pharmaceutical industry.
- To find out factors responsible for attracting potential talents to pharmaceutical sectors.
- To suggest strategies to retain missionary sales employees.

Research Framework

Mohanty& Pany/ Talent Management Of Missionary Sales Force For Low Attrition Rate

Medical representative job quit is greatly influenced by different factors. The diagram below shows the relationship of medical representative job quit with different factors. In this study job Quit is dependent upon five independents factors. The job quit is a dependent variable which depends on other variables such as Sale pressure, Career Advancement, Employee Management relation, Compensation, and Organizational Image. But it is important to find which factor has greater impact on employee turnover.

METHODOLOGY

Sources of Study

The study is based on primary data collected from managers of different cadre in selected companies have been approached with the help of a structured questionnaire. However, secondary data is collected from journals, text books, etc. The questionnaires contained both open and closed ended questions.

Data collection

For data collection the medical representative of five medicine companies, like Pfizer, Novartis, Glaxo Smithkline, Nicholas Piramal, abbot Pharmaceuticals were taken as sample. Samples of 100 pharma employees were contacted for data collection. 82 questionnaires were received back and 2 were discarded because of incompleteness. For the final analysis 80 responses were considered. The employees were of top management, senior management, middle management and junior management cadre.

Analysis of Data:

Table 1: Reasons for leaving the organization

Mohanty& Pany/ Talent Management Of Missionary Sales Force For Low Attrition Rate

	Top Management%	Senior Management%	Middle Management%	Junior Management%
a.Better Compensation	18.00	38.00	60.00	62.00
b.Employee & Management relationship	4.0	4.0	14.00	20.00
c. Career advancement	26.00	42.00	56.00	48.00
d. Sales Pressure	16.00	24.00	36.00	44.00
e.Organizational Image	8.0	6.0	8.0	20.00

The pharma sales people used to be dissatisfied and tend to demotivate due to the various factors which results in high attrition rate. Most of the time the pharma sales people feel their job insecure because they have to achieve the over ambitious target at any cost set by the top management. As in every month the sales force has to achieve the high target and in return, in spite of getting reward they will be overburdened with new and fresh high target which increases work pressure with the sales force. The job of the pharma sales force involves extensive travelling for which they have to stay away from their family and fails to maintain a good balance between their work and family life. Even though the pharma sales people work very hard physically as well as mentally throughout out the year against all odds and are very dynamic and challenging but their profession is not socially honored and is not properly recognized, also the monthly salary and incentive policy are not lucrative enough to motivate them. In this profession the key players like the doctors, retailers, stockiest, C&Fs etc, do not show good behavior towards the

pharma sales people which results in the feeling of low self esteem among them. The job profile of the pharma sales people at the same position is routine and monotonous which becomes a boring factor for the plateaued sales force at the age of around 45. Even though there is a provision of yearly leave in some companies but the pharma sales people most of the time unable to avail it due to heavy workload. Peers cooperation does neither motivate nor demotivate the Pharma sales people, as they are geographically separated. In some pooled territories the cooperation among the peers is hostile in nature due to the heavy sales target. Some limited pharma companies have bright future career for their sales force whereas in other pharma companies do not have those career opportunities. The pharma sales force hardly gets any chance for participating in the company decision making policy.

STRATEGIES TO REDUCE ATTRITION:

Attract Best Talents: Employees are key to success of any organization. Organization should attract best talents from the sources as a preferred employer. Sales department needs different talents. The emphasis should be given in locating, attracting and selecting best talents who wants to make sales as their best career. Many a times young talents do not continue in sales because they make it a stop gap arrangement.

Focus on training & Development: Training helps in identifying the potential talent from employees and later helps to sharpen their latent skills. Training programs like behavioral programs, leadership and other managerial programs can help groom employees further in line with their career paths and aspirations. Pharmaceutical companies on a fast growth track will have to focus on managing their star performers as well.

Emphasis to Retain Good Employees: Retention of talented employees is always the most important agenda for any company to grow. While good compensation can be a hygiene factor in talent management, only monetary benefits may not be attractive to retain them. Giving them higher salaries, Faster growth opportunities, Better performance based bonus amounts, advanced training opportunities, Recognition award ,Reflects in the salary increase, projects abroad etc. are some factors which helps in retaining good performers in organization.

Psychological Support: Employees in pharmaceutical companies are generally intellectual staff and hence the psychological relationship between leaders and employees is very crucial. Professionals who contribute to organizational competitive edge directly want a high degree of organizational recognition that their ideas are important. They expect their leaders to be intellectually on their plane but they do not want a leader's talent and skills to outshine their own.

Proper Career track management: While employees are more seeking job advancement and job achievement, challenging and growing career path, career track planning is important. "Career track planning can be done by developing comprehensive career growth plans for existing talents some talented employees are highly individualistic. Providing mentors for them to become good team members and team leaders is another workable method."

Organizational environment & Climate : Organizational environment like work culture, engaged leaders, effective communication practices, challenging assignments, international exposure, flexible work-time, quality of life, work-life-balance, etc. can increase employee engagement and improve productivity. Good working atmosphere, better opportunities, career planning, international opportunities for good performers, strong meritocracy, regular and timely rewards can reduce attrition rate considerably. Industry sources point out those pharmaceutical companies must not only attract talent but also foster an environment in which their clever people are inspired to achieve their fullest potential in a way that produces wealth and value for all stakeholders.

Mohanty& Pany/ Talent Management Of Missionary Sales Force For Low Attrition Rate

Besides above for reducing the attrition rate of pharma companies, some initiatives can be taken which are given below:

- The security of 'having the job'. Because the Pharma sales people are always in the tension of 'not having the job'.
- Family insurance policy or group insurance policy can be a driving force.
- Incentive policy or performance allowance is needed to revise.
- Holiday should be holiday and it should be ensured for the family members.
- Mandatory yearly leave availing can be ensured.
- Well defined career path should be spelled out.
- Fixed salary part need to be hiked.
- Sufficient training for the future career path.
- Achievable monthly sales target should be set with proper calculation.
- Implementation of Sales Force Automation i.e. the sales force will not have to carry heavy sales kit.
- Provision for Financial and Non financial benefits (More fringe benefits).
- MBO practices in the organization can improve relationship.
- Posting in local areas can reduce cultural shock and pressure.
- Proper control over unethical business practices.
- Better conveyance and mobile phone allowance.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the research it is clear and concluded that all factors like Sale pressure, Career Advancement, Employee Management relation, Employee- Employee relations, Compensation and Organizational Image has a significant positive influence on medical representatives of Pharmaceuticals firms. Study represents that compensation is the most important player for job quit of medical representative as compare to all other variables. Organizational Brand image, career advancement and employee-employee relation are the second, third and fourth key player for the job quit of medical representative. While other factors like work life balance, low self esteem, group medi-claim facility factors have less impact on job quit of medical representative of Pharmaceuticals firm.

With changes and innovations in the human resource management's strategy, using tools like. Good recruitment strategy, Development and training, Talent retention strategy, Good psychological relationship, Organizational culture, Career track management, it is possible to reduce attrition in the pharmaceutical industry.

REFERENCES

Robbins, P., and Judge, T. A. (2007). "Organizational behaviour." 12th edition, New Jersey, Pearson Education, Inc.
Sekaran, U. (2003). "Research method for business: A skill building approach." 4th edition, USA, John Wiley & Sons.

Stallworth, H. L. (2003). "Mentoring, organizational commitment and intentions to leave public accounting." *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 18, 405 – 415

Trinka, J. A. (2005). "What's a manager to do?" *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 37, 154 – 159.

Tymon Jr, W. G., Stumpf, S. A., and Smith, R. R. (2011). "Manager support predicts turnover of professionals in India." *Career Development International*, 16, 293 – 312.

Vos, A. D., and Meganck, A. (2009). "What HR managers do versus what employees value: Exploring both parties' views on retention management from a psychological contract perspective." *Personnel Review*, 38, 45 – 60.

Hong EC, Hao LZ, Kumar R, Ramendran C, Kadiresan V (2012). An Effectiveness of Human Resource Management Practices on Employee Retention in Institute of Higher learning. *International J. Business Research and Management (IJBRM)*, Vol.3 (2), pp.60-79

Iverson RD, Currivan DB (2003). "Union participation, job satisfaction, and employee turnover: An event-history analysis of the exit-voice hypothesis". *Industrial Relations*, 42, 101-105.

Kasmi Z, Zakaria R, Bagh R (2011). Employee Retention: A Challenge for HR Practitioners. *Clear International J. Commerce and management*, Vol-01, pp 31-42

Nelson B (1995, November). "Motivating employees with informal awards". *Management accounting (USA)*, 77, 30-35.

Sohail N, Muneer A, Tanveer Y, Tariq H (2011). Losing Your Best Talent: Employee Retention The Dilemma Of Textile Industry A Case Of Textile Sector. *Interdisciplinary J. Contemporary Research In Business*, Vol 3(8), pp. 896-906

Sundeji MG (2004). Employee Retention and Turnover: The Real Reasons Employees Stay or Go. *FMI Journal*, Vol.15(2), pp.37-48

Ahmad, Z., Ahmad, Z., Ahmed, Z., and Nawaz, M. M. (2010). "Organizational climate (oc) as employees' satisfier: Empirical evidence from pharmaceutical sector." *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5, 214-222.

Anis, A., Rehman, K., Rehman, I., Khan, M. A., and Humayoun, A. A. (2011). "Impact of organizational commitment on job satisfaction and employee retention in pharmaceutical industry." *African Journal of Business Management*, 5, 7316-7324.

Anvari, R., Amin, S. M., Ismail, W. K. W., Ahmad, U. N. U., and Seliman, S. (2011). "Mediating effects of affective organizational commitment and psychological contract in the relationship between strategic training practices and knowledge sharing." *African Journal of Business Management*, 5, 2189-2202.